

THE ROLE OF MULTIMEDIA ELEMENTS IN THE PREPARATION OF PORTRAIT LONGRID

Iroda Z. Nasimova - a doctoral student of the Journalism and mass
communications university of Uzbekistan

Abstract

This article talks about the aspects that should be paid attention to when preparing a portrait longride, which is becoming popular today in foreign Internet publications, the main stages of creating material in this format, and the possibilities of multimedia platforms.

Key words: Portrait longrid, storytelling, multimedia elements, effects, interactivity, pricing.

Today, preparation of material in longread format is gaining popularity as the main format in foreign press and internet publications. Women's longrids are mostly made in portrait form or storytelling format. Information consumers have developed the ability to receive short text messages or large volumes of information together with multimedia tools in the era of digital media. Multimediaization has become a natural step in the development of world journalism.

The unlimited possibilities of the Internet made it possible to “breathe life” into multimedia stories. The material is supplemented with text, video interviews, audio effects, infographics, facts and audiovisual elements. This is not just an audiovisual product, but a full-fledged journalistic material, which ensures that the reader is not distracted or bored. Such comprehensive materials help to delve deep into a voluminous subject. Effective use of multimedia elements and storytelling helps to solve the editorial social tasks of engaging the audience in complex, multifaceted stories.

The hero's portrait, thoughts, and life conclusions are mainly expressed on the basis of photography, animation, and a variety of color palettes in the portrait longrid. The audience reading it should have a figurative perception of the hero, get a typical idea about him through the combination of words and images. For example, the material “Glitter in the dark” published in 2021 on pikchfort.com is a clear proof of our idea.

The subject and content of the material: the dark life of a singer and musician named Natasha Khan is illuminated by the language of the author and character. Form to match content changes through Natasha Khan's animated typed photos. The methods of artistic representation characteristic of the portrait essay began with the introduction. A special emphasis is placed on the places where the hero's childhood and adulthood have passed. From the first successful songs to periods of creative

depression, the history of the birth of popular music will be revealed in a consistent manner. The hero's thoughts are quoted.

Content of portrait longrid: The material consists of more than 3100 words and is a large volume. Changing pictures while reading texts does not make the audience bored with the material.

Type of multimedia elements: In this portrait essay, the sequence of events, the hero's mental state, mood, his photos, clothes are shown. The portrait essay is divided into four parts. Each part is distinguished by a separate quote on the web page. 74 images were used to make the animation. Located on a separate web page. The mental state of the hero is presented in pictures, and his difficulties are presented simply and clearly in black and white colors. Although the text font is small, it does not tire the reader.

“Sewing a lifelong dream” published on nrc.com¹, the official website of the Norwegian Refugee Council, is a vivid proof of our opinion. On this site, portraits of people who have overcome all difficulties are published in a modern format about the life of refugees. The organization was launched after World War II and has been providing food, education, shelter, legal aid and protection from violence to refugees of various nationalities.

The topic and content of the material: It describes the life path, fate, and experiences of Gulistan, a Syrian Kurd who was forced to move and flee due to the war. His life path goes from Al-Hasakah to Dohuk. Despite the planes, gunshots and screams, mental and physical pressures, a woman's companion is a sewing machine, scissors and a tape measure, shown through high-level infographics and maps.

Methodological features of the text: the material is narrated from the beginning to the end in the language of the hero. The socio-economic situation in Syria and the life of refugees are described against the background of a woman who loves her profession and her destiny. Dates are also mentioned in connection with political processes.

The project has a vertical structure that opens on a separate web page. For the background, the necessary details of the tailoring profession were moved and increased the interactivity of the material.

Multimedia elements: 31 photos, background for seam of the car static 4 photos, 2 videophones; iterative map 1, online link 5.

How long will such longrids be ready? Where to start, which platforms will make it easier to use?

¹ [Love each lifelong dream \(nrc.no\)](http://Love each lifelong dream (nrc.no))

First, it is necessary to have a team approach to such materials at the project level. First, the idea of what topic to create material was worked on, and the topic is selected.

Secondly, a team of specialists is formed, such as a creative employee to write, edit, work with archives, and a designer, editor, and photographer to create high-quality visual components.

Thirdly, before preparing any multimedia projects, it is necessary to divide the processes into three stages: study, preparation, transmission. Each of them is a process that requires special work and knowledge. Depending on whether the material is on a historical or modern topic, tasks and activities such as contacting sources, where and how to collect archival documents, interviewing whom are planned.

Fourth, a number of organizational processes for the preparation of the topic, in particular, the preparation of an official letter for obtaining information from organizations (if necessary), and the study of the topic through electronic sources until the deadline for its response are determined.

Fifth, interviews and photos are sorted, based on the documents, a plan of who will say what and where, which instrument or photo, music will be used, and the text of the script is written.

Sixth, the finished text is edited and posted online on a platform that designs internet materials, just as newspaper text is placed in separate design programs. If the sources contain information from the Internet itself, they are placed in the program itself through hyperlinks and the publish button is pressed.

First of all, the continuity of the materials in multimedia format in national internet publications increases the interest of the viewer or reader in quality content. In order to increase them, first of all, it is necessary to have a special department or team working in Internet publications, to develop a fee tariff for each material, and to formulate a concept of selling (monetization) of the material. Depending on the size of the material, it can take a minimum of 2 weeks and a maximum of 2 months with the full attention of a small or large team. It depends on the topic, size and goals of the work.

It is appropriate to dwell on what programs or platforms a journalist can effectively use to prepare multimedia material in modern formats.

The **Shorthand.com** platform has the following advantages for creating multimedia materials:

Interactivity - platform sliders, map widgets, animation and pop-ups provide unusualness in the material. It depends on the ability of the journalist to convey the

information and the right content strategy.

The ability to use all formats of multi-contents - infographics, photos and videos, audio and other multimedia elements makes it easier to read large texts, increases awareness of the topic being conveyed.

Convenience - the platform can create content without using "html" or other complex algorithms, and the author can work on independent complex designs with the help of an intuitive editor. The user can also read it whether on a computer, tablet or phone. It is convenient for the user to know in advance how it will look on each technical device and to transfer elements in a separate perspective for small screen devices .

Ease of publication - once the material is ready, you can independently set the time of publication and share the web address as much as you want. After the publication of the material, it calculates all the analyzes about which part of it was most viewed and how many minutes it was read.

These capabilities help convey context in a visual format through several other platforms, including sites such as tilda.com, medium.com, narratively.com, storymaps (storyMapJS, arcGIS StoryMaps, etc.).

Preparation of high-quality and interactive content encourages the clip-like generation to patiently read long materials and be interested. However, multimedia materials require a professional approach, and a single author must have sufficient competence in several areas, so the number of such contents is small.

For the consumer who does not want any other choice than receiving information via the Internet, the use of methods that attract the attention and interest of the audience, the use of methods that bring out the material to the level of the product, advertising - these are the aspects that ensure a lot of reading of modern multimedia materials.